

THE DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH

Xudoyberdiyeva Nargiza Odil qizi

Termiz State University

Theory and practice of translation

+(998) 95-056-81-81

Rahmatullayeva Iroda Valijon qizi

Termiz State University

Theory and practice of translation

+(998) 99-203-8821

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205236>

Abstract. This article deals with the problem of possible difficulties in translating from English into Russian. It is shown that understanding the text is a skill that requires hard work. The problems that may arise in the translation of texts are analyzed. Difficulties connected with translation are classified and the characteristic of the selected problems of translation is given.

Some recommendations are given to help in translating English texts into Russian. The interpreter should know and see the problems he can meet and be able to avoid them.

Key words: translation, foreign texts, homonyms, grammar, vocabulary.

ТРУДНОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрена проблема возможных трудностей при переводе с английского языка на русский. Показано, что понимание текста - это навык, который требует упорного труда. Проанализированы проблемы, которые могут возникнуть при переводе текстов. Классифицированы трудности, связанные с переводом и дана характеристика выделенным проблемам перевода. Приведены некоторые рекомендации, которые помогут при переводе английских текстов на русский язык.

Переводчик должен знать и видеть проблемы, с которыми он может встретиться и уметь их избегать.

Ключевые слова: перевод, иноязычные тексты, омонимы, грамматика, лексика.

Currently, many linguists note that an amazing thing is happening. A linguistic revolution associated primarily with the scientific and technological revolution. Each word has its own history, even those that appeared spontaneously [1, p. 11].

Words are the most vibrant part of language; they are connected with all spheres of human society, politics, sports, technology, science and art, this is the area in which they formed to provide the necessary connection for existence human activity. Understanding the origins of words is powerful source of technical development of terminology [2, p. 8].

Most words in English are ambiguous with different interpretations; words can mean different things in different contexts, especially concerning technical terms.

Translation is the communication of intentions, feelings and implicit messages without compromising subtleties, features and inherent beauty of language. Translation means simultaneous communication and poetry [2, p. 13].

Translators usually have to deal with six different problem areas in their work, be it the translation of technical documents or assurance. These include lexical-semantic problems, grammar, syntax, rhetoric, pragmatic and cultural issues.

1. Lexica-semantic problems can be solved by referring to dictionaries, glossaries, terminology banks and experts. These issues include terminological alternatives, neologisms, semantic gaps, contextual synonyms and antonyms (they affect polysemantic units: synonyms and antonyms are aimed only at acceptance, which depends on the context, to determine which meaning is correct), semantic contiguity (a matching procedure that works by defining semantic features common to two or more terms) and lexical networks.

2. Grammar problems include, for example, issues of tense, aspectuality (appearance shows how a process or state is represented, expressed by the verb in terms of its development, as opposed to the tense itself), pronouns and whether an explicit subject pronoun follows or not.

3. Syntactic problems may arise due to syntactic parallels, direction of the passive voice, focus (the point of view from which the history) or even rhetorical figures of speech such as hyperbaton (inversion natural order of speech)) or anaphora (repetition of a word or segment at the beginning lines or phrases).

4. Rhetorical problems involve identifying and reconstructing figures. thoughts (comparison, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, oxymoron, paradox, etc.) and diction.

5. Pragmatic problems arise from differences in formal and informal ways of addressing using “you”, as well as idiomatic phrases, sayings, irony, humor and sarcasm.

6. Cultural problems can arise due to differences between cultural references such as food names, festivals and cultural connotations in general. The translator will use language localization to correctly adapt the translation to the target culture. A very simple example – financial translation that includes dates.

The table below shows some recommendations when translating English texts.

Table 1. Recommendations

№	Recommendations
1	Extensive reading aloud of English texts can help develop reading skills and at the same time reduce the number of errors
2	Acquiring encyclopedic knowledge can form deep basic knowledge to improve your translation abilities. Various genres such as novels, television series, documentaries, songs, comics and academic articles are recommended in order to expose their wide variety of linguistic usage, which in turn will allow you to correctly interpret the text.
3	The use of dictionaries helps in translating texts in English. But we should remember the different meanings that a word can have, and various parts of speech that can influence propositional meaning.
4	Reading and writing develop linguistic awareness, which forces you to constantly monitor your translation.

The exclusivity of text conversion from Russian to English lies in the tangible difference between the two languages. For good understanding the meaning of a foreign language text, it is necessary not only to study individual complex cases, but also to gain systemic knowledge.

Polysemy viewed diachronically, historical change semantic structure of the word, leading to new meanings, added to the already existing in the rearrangement of these meanings in its semantic structure. Since semantic structure is never static, the relationship between diachronic and synchronic assessment of individual meanings of the same word may be different in different periods of the historical development of a language.

It is necessary to take into account the diversity of terminology when translating technical texts correctly. Undoubtedly, engineers of a specific industries that speak the language can translate technical texts better, because that they know the subject of translation. However, knowledge of polysemantic terms will help you cope with the translation task.

REFERENCES

1. Solijonov Juraali Kamoljnovich. (2022). Lingua-perspective Problems and Solutions of Translating the Plant and Food Names in the "Harry Potter" books from English into Uzbek. *ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development*, Vol 39(No 4.), 221–229. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6607317 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6607317>
2. Kamoljnovich, S. J. (2022). JK ROULINGNING FANTASTIK ASARLARIDAGI ANTROPONIMLARNING LINGVO-PERSPEKTIV MUAMMOLARI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(1), 334-343. <https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-2454-2022-1-334-343>
3. Kamoljonovich, S. J., & O'G, Y. N. U. B. (2022). BADIY TARJIMA UCHUN TARJIMA USULLARI TAHLILI (IAN TUHOVSKIY ASARLARI MISOLIDA). *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 18(5), 32-37.
4. Jo'ramurodova, Z., & Solijonov, J. (2022, April). JK ROULINGNING "BIDL QISSANAVIS ERTAKLARI" ("THE TALES OF BEEDLE THE BARD") ASARIDAGI ANTROPONIMLARNING O'ZBEK TILIDAN INGLIZ TILIGA TARJIMA QILISHDAGI MUAMMOLARI. In *МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ: "СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАДИГМЫ: ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЕ ТРАДИЦИЙ И ИННОВАЦИЙ II"* (Vol. 2, No. 18.03, pp. 554-560). <https://doi.org/10.47100/nuu.v2i18.03.115>
5. Arnold I.V. *Stylistics. Modern English* / I.V. Arnold. - M.:Flint; 5th edition, rev. and additional, 2002. - 384 p.
6. Bezkorovaynaya G.T. *Methods of representing the semantic field gentleness / nobleness and correlation of component values: synchronic aspect (on Material of English fiction of the 19th century // Lexicology and phraseology (Roman-Germanic cycle)*. St. Petersburg, 2011.- 231 p.
7. Vezhbitskaya A.P. *Understanding Cultures through Keywords /Vezhbitskaya, Anna*. M.: Languages of Slavic culture, 2001. - 288 p.
8. Vvedenskaya L.A. *Etymology: Textbook* / L.A. Vvedenskaya, N.P. Kolesnikov. M.: St. Petersburg: Peter, 2004. 221 p.